

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Overview Of Sustained Release Beads

Bhumika Kolse*, Disha Ramdham, Ayushi Sabane, Bhumika Gandhre, Koshish Gabhane, Vikrant Salode, Nilesh Banarase

P. R. Patil Institute of Pharmacy, Talegaon, Ashti, Wardha, 442202, Maharashtra, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 13 Oct 2025

Keywords:

Food poisoning and spoilage, *Caesalpinia pulcherrima*, Extracts, Antimicrobial activity

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17337129

ABSTRACT

With continuous increase in the human population, the cases of food poisoning and spoilage are on the rise. Such spoilage of foods to avoid the growth of unwanted microorganisms in order to protect from poisoning is generally achieved by the use of preservatives. But due to continuous exposure of the microorganism with the same preservatives have been resulted to create resistance against it. So, in order to search for the new preservatives, the petroleum ether, chloroform, acetone, methanol and aqueous extracts of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* (L.) leaves have been examined against *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Aspergillus niger* HN-2 microorganisms for antimicrobial activity. The conducted experimental results clearly indicated about its ability to restrict the growth of tested microorganisms generally responsible for food poisoning and spoilage. Since, the previous reported toxicity studies already showed its safety profile, these plant extracts can surely be the matter of alternative choice as food preservatives.

INTRODUCTION

Food poisoning resulted due to microbial contamination presents a significant public and economic health problem for human society. Amongst many strategies for inhibiting the growth of undesirable microorganisms, in order to avoid food spoilage and ultimately to poisoning, is the use of chemical agents commonly known as ‘preservatives’. [1] Various kinds of microorganisms such as gram negative bacteria

like *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* along with gram positive like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus* and fungi like *Aspergillus niger* are common food spoiler. Most outbreaks of *Escherichia coli*, rod-shaped gram-negative bacteria, had been linked with the consumption of undercooked products, pork sausages and salami. The ability of *Escherichia coli* to adapt to acidic environment in gastro intestinal tract made it as one of the most dangerous pathogens in the food

***Corresponding Author:** Bhumika Kolse

Address: P. R. Patil Institute of Pharmacy, Talegaon, Ashti, Wardha, 442202, Maharashtra, India.

Email ✉: kolsebhum@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

products. [2, 3] *Aspergillus niger* is a fungus responsible for the disease called ‘black mold’ to fruits and vegetables as well as a common food contaminant.[4] While, *Bacillus cereus* is estimated to be responsible for 1%–12% of all food poisoning outbreaks worldwide with diarrheal and emetic syndrome.[5-13]

Although chemical preservatives have proven its efficient role in controlling the growth of such undesired microorganisms, but still, newer ways are required to avoid their unpleasant side effects as well as growing microbial resistances as a serious concern. For such purposes, researchers are focusing the use of plant extracts with antimicrobial activities as preservatives due to its relative safety. [14]

Caesalpinia pulcherrima (L.) (Family- Fabaceae) commonly known as ‘peacock flower’ is widely known ornamental tree distributed throughout the tropical and sub-tropical region including India, China, Africa and native to West Indies. [15, 16]

C. pulcherrima reported to have various pharmacological activities like anthelmintic, antimalarial, antidiabetic and antimicrobial attributed to richness of phytoconstituents like saponins, terpenoids, tannins, alkaloids and many more. [17-20] Various scientific studies have concluded the relative safety of *C. pulcherrima* leaf extracts with LD₅₀ value of more than 2,000 – 4,000 mg/kg in experimental Wistar albino rats and mice respectively. [21, 22] Due to all such findings, our main objective of the study was to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of *C. pulcherrima* leaf extracts against food borne pathogenic and spoilage bacteria and fungi namely *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Aspergillus niger* HN-2 respectively.

Review Of Literature

SUMMARY AND DISCUSSIONS

Conflict Of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge the library facility of the college for this work.

REFERENCES

1. Amensour M, Bouhdid S, Fernandez-Lopez J, Idaomar M, Senhaji NS, Abrini J. Antibacterial activity of extracts of *Myrtus communis* against food-borne pathogenic and spoilage bacteria. *Int J Food Prop.* 2010; 13(6): 1215-1224.
2. Hakim AS, Abuelnaga ASM, Ezz-Eldeen AM, Bakry MA, Ismail SA. Prevalence of some food poisoning bacteria in local and imported retail pork by-products in Egyptian markets. *Afr J Microbiol Res.* 2015; 9(22): 1492-1498.
3. Sachidananda Swamy HC, Asha MM, Chaithra M, Vivek MN, Kambar Y, Prashith Kekuda TR. Antibacterial activity of flower extract of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima*, *Delonix regia* and *Peltaphorum ferrugineum* against Urinary tract Pathogens. *Int Res J Biological Sci.* 2014; 3(4): 80-83.
4. Sharma R. Pathogenicity of *Aspergillus niger* in plants. *Cibtech J Microbiol.* 2012; 1: 47-51.
5. Dagenais TR, Keller NP. Pathogenesis of *Aspergillus fumigatus* in Invasive Aspergillosis. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2009; 22(3): 447-465.
6. Tewari A, Abdullah S. *Bacillus cereus* food poisoning: International and Indian perspective. *J Food Sci Technol.* 2015; 52(5): 2500-2511.

7. Gupta V, Singh S, Gupta YK. Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes N-O-S donor ligands. *Asian J Pharm Ana.* 2014; 4(4): 174-177.
8. Killedar SG, More HN. Screening of antimicrobial potential and phytoconstituents for different extracts of *Memecylon umbellatum* Burm Inflorescences. *Asian J Pharm Res.* 2011; 1(4): 114-118.
9. Paul S, Saha D. Comparative study of the efficacy of *Barleria prionitis* leaf extracts against bacteria. *Asian J Pharm Res.* 2012; 2(3): 107-110.
10. Mohite SA, Shah RR, Patel NR. Antimicrobial activity of leaves extracts of *Jatropha curcas*. *Asian J Pharm Res.* 2018; 8(1): 17-20.
11. Mohite S, Shah R, Patel N. Antimicrobial activity of leaves extracts of *Passiflora foetida*. *Asian J Res Pharm Sci.* 2018; 8(1): 17-20.
12. Meera R, Devi P, Madhumitha B, Kameswari B. Antibacterial activity of crude extracts and semi synthetic hydrazone derivatives of *Rimelia reticulata*. *Asian J Research Chem.* 2009; 2(4): 445-447.
13. Granum PE, Lund T. *Bacillus cereus* and its food poisoning toxins. *FEMS Microbiol Lett.* 1997; 157(2): 223-228.
14. Mostafa AA, Al-Askar AA, Almaary KS, Dawoud TM, Sholkamy EN, Bakri MM. Antimicrobial activity of some plant extracts against bacterial strains causing food poisoning diseases. *Saudi J Biol Sci.* 2018; 25(2): 361-366.
15. Lukita B, Budiardjo S, Elya B. Evaluation of the antimicrobial activity of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* (L) Swartz extract against microbes that cause dental and oral infections and determination of the total flavonoid and total phenolic contents of the plant. *Iran J Pharm Sci.* 2019; 15(4): 1-10.
16. Osuntokun OT, Julianah JU, Thonda OA. Bioprospective screening of antibacterial and phytochemical activity of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* (pride of Barbados) on selected clinical isolate. *Bioequiv & Bioavailab Int J.* 2017; 1(3): 000118.
17. Patil N, Vaishnav RL, Thanusubramanian H, Holla SN, Manohar HD, Bairy KL. Formulation and evaluation of the hydroalcoholic extract of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* (Stem bark) on wound healing model in wistar rats. *Int J Adv Res.* 2015; 3(3): 648-654.
18. Sasi Premila JM, Sreeja N. Preliminary phytochemical, antioxidant and antimicrobial analysis of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima*. *World J Pharm Res.* 2018; 7(5): 1400-1408.
19. Mallapur S, Biradar PR, Kavatagimath SA, Patil P, Kudatarkar N. Pharmacological evaluation of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* leaf extract for anticancer activity against Ehrlich Ascites Carcinoma bearing mice. *Indian J Pharm Edu Res.* 2021; 55(1): 164-173.
20. Faloye K, Famuyiwa S, Akinwunmi K, Tata C, Ayoola M, Fakola E, Akinyele O, Ndinteh D. Antioxidant potentials of the pod extract of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* Swartz (Fabaceae) and the theoretical evaluation of the antioxidant property of the isolated compounds. *Res Sq.* 2021; DOI: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-1137829/v1.
21. Sharma V, Rajani GP. Evaluation of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* Linn. for anti-inflammatory and antiulcer activities. *Indian J Pharmacol.* 2011; 43(2): 168-171.
22. Kumar S, Singh J, Baghotia A, Mehta V, Thakur V, Choudhary M, Verma S, Kumar D. Antifertility potential of the ethanolic extract of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* Linn. leaves. *Asian Pac J Reprod.* 2013; 2(2): 90-92.
23. Kokate CK. *Practical Pharmacognosy.* Vallabh Prakashan, 2014.

24. Banarase N, Khadabadi S, Sawarkar H. Pharmacognosy practicals (an illustrative guide). Scholar's Press, 2018.
25. Khandelwal KR, Sethi V. Practical pharmacognosy (techniques and experiments). Nirali Prakashan, 2016.
26. Narasimhan R, Satiyamoorthy M. Phytochemical screening and antioxidant studies in the pulp extracts of *Cucurbita maxima*. *Asian J Pharm Res.* 2016; 6(1): 01-04.
27. Roy A, Bhoumik D, Sahu RA, Dwivedi J. Phytochemical screening and antioxidant activity of *Sesbania grandiflora* leaves extracts. *Asian J Res Pharm Sci.* 2014; 4(1): 16-21.
28. Morris SS, Jayabalan G, Jha AK, Verma S, Swarnkar Y. Phytochemical screening and in-vitro anthelmintic activity of seed extracts of plants *Carum carvi* of Family Apiaceae. *Asian J Res Pharm Sci.* 2016; 6(4): 246-254.
29. Mouli JBC, Madhu C. Reddy KR, Lakshmi PJ. Omar Md. Comparative Studies on Phytochemical screening and metal analysis of alcoholic extracts of *Musa acuminata*, *Actinidia deliciosa* and *Mangifer indica* by using ICPOES and Flame Photometer. *Asian J Res Pharm Sci.* 2019; 9(2): 78-84.
30. Balouiri M, Sadiki M, Ibsouda SK. Methods for in vitro evaluating antimicrobial activity: A review. *J Pharm Anal.* 2016; 6(2): 71-79.
31. Sanchez E, Morales CR, Castillo S, Leos-Rivas C, Garcia-Becerra L, Martinez DMO. Antibacterial and antibiofilm activity of methanolic plant extracts against Nosocomial microorganisms. *Evid-based Complement Altern Med.* 2016, 2016: 1572697.

HOW TO CITE: Bhumika Kolve*, Disha Ramdham, Ayushi Sabane, Bhumika Gandhre, Koshish Gabhane, Vikrant Salode, Nilesh Banarase, Overview of Sustained Release Beads, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 10, 1102-1107 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17337129>

Fig. 1: Antimicrobial assay against (A)- *Bacillus cereus*, (B)- *Escherichia coli* and (C)- *Aspergillus niger* HN-2; Et- Ethanolic extract, Aq- Aqueous extract, Ac- Acetone extract, Ch- Chloroform extract, Pe- Petroleum ether extract and C- Control

Table 1: Phytochemical screening

Phytoconstituents	Tests	Petroleum ether extract	Chloroform extract	Acetone extract	Ethanol extract	Aqueous extract
Carbohydrates	Molisch's	-	-	-	+	+
	Fehling's	-	-	-	+	+
	Barfoed's	-	-	-	+	+
	Bial's Orcinol	-	-	-	+	+
	Selwinoff's	-	-	-	+	+
	Tollen's phloroglucinol	-	-	-	+	+
Proteins	Biuret	-	-	-	-	+
	Million's	-	-	-	-	+
	Sulphur containing	-	-	-	-	+
Alkaloids	Mayer's	+	-	+	-	-
	Wagner's	+	-	+	-	-

	Hager's	+	-	+	-	-
	Dragendroff's	+	-	+	-	-
Saponin glycosides	Foam	-	+	-	+	+
	Haemolysis	-	+	-	+	+
Anthraquinone glycosides	Borntrager's	-	-	-	-	-
Steroids	Salkowski's	+	+	-	-	-
	Legal's	+	+	-	-	-
Flavonoids	Shinoda	+	+	+	+	+
Terpenoids	Salkowaski's	+	+	+	+	-
	Liebermann-Burchard's	+	+	+	+	-
Tannins	Ferric chloride	+	+	+	+	+
	Lead acetate	+	+	+	+	+
	Potassium dichromate	+	+	+	+	+
	Gelatin	+	+	+	+	+
Amino acids	Ninhydrin	-	-	-	-	+

+ represents "present" and - represents "absent"

Table 2: Antimicrobial assay and MIC

Extracts	Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)		
	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger HN-2</i>
Petroleum ether	50 mg/ml	80 mg/ml	> 100 mg/ml
Chloroform	> 100 mg/ml	> 100 mg/ml	> 100 mg/ml
Acetone	> 100 mg/ml	40 mg/ml	40 mg/ml
Ethanol	> 100 mg/ml	> 100 mg/ml	> 100 mg/ml
Aqueous	> 100 mg/ml	> 100 mg/ml	> 100 mg/ml